

Investigation of the use of different filling materials in unsaturated vertical flow constructed wetlands for the treatment of UASB effluent from domestic wastewater

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Abstract

The selection of the appropriate filling material in constructed wetlands (CWs), depends on the required treatment, the cost, availability and the hydraulic behaviour of the system. This work examined materials of various origins (recycled glass, biochar and gel beads), that can be used in unsaturated vertical sub-surface flow CWs and were compared to sand. The suitability of the materials was initially determined by their granulometry and porosity, that affect hydraulic conductivity (sand 0.23, recycled glass 0.16 and biochar 0.04 cm/s). Preliminary results for the treatment of anaerobic effluents produced by a UASB process treating domestic wastewater indicated promising performance of the materials without any clogging. Under $OLR = 5.5 \pm 0.8$ gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹, $SLR = 2.8 \pm 0.5$ gTSS m⁻² d⁻¹ and $NLR = 1.1 \pm 0.2$ gNH₄-N m⁻² d⁻¹, the TSS and COD removal was >80% and ammonium removal >90%, aided by the initial adsorption capacity.

Keywords

Constructed wetlands; filling material; wastewater treatment; hydraulic conductivity

INTRODUCTION

Various materials have been used as an alternative to sand that is usually used as filling material in vertical sub-surface flow constructed wetlands (VSSF CWs) such as polyethylene terephthalate (Sandoval-Herazo et al., 2018), recycled glass (Humeniuk et al., 2019), dimension stones and bricks (Marcelino et al., 2020) and biochar (Gupta et al., 2016). The selection of the filling materials depends on the treatment requirements and therefore the required removal of pollutants e.g., organic matter, nutrients, heavy metals, surfactants and emerging contaminants (Wang et al., 2020) and, thus, the required removal mechanism. The orientation of wastewater treatment has been shifting from safe-to-discharge to safe-to-reuse effluent; the preservation of nutrients in the treated effluent is of crucial importance. Materials that precipitate phosphorus e.g., those that have Ca content >10% (Moreno-Perez et al., 2018) should be avoided. The present work investigated the suitability of three different filling materials (recycled glass, hydrogels and biochar) in comparison to sand for the treatment of anaerobic effluents produced by a UASB process treating domestic wastewater.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Four columns packed with each substrate were implemented to simulate VSSF unsaturated (UNSAT) CW (Figure 1). Coarse gravel covered the bottom 20 cm as drainage, while 20 cm of finer gravel was

placed on top of it to support the main filter media, whose total height was 40 cm. On top of the main filter media 20 cm of the same fine gravel was placed to distribute wastewater uniformly to the filter media. The diameter of each column was 25cm. The first tests of the materials included granulometry, porosity and hydraulic conductivity determination.

Figure 1. Layout of the four simulation columns (sand, gels, recycled glass, biochar)

Granulometry

Sand, Glass & Biochar

Granulometry was determined by sieving to produce the granulometric curve. Since fine media was required for VSSF UNSAT CWs, sieves of 2, 1, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.1 mm were used.

Hydrogels

The gels were commercially available of biodegradable polymer origin and standard uniform size so there was no need for granulometry determination, since the expanded gel (after water absorption) was spherical with 8 – 10 mm diameter.

Porosity calculation (n)

The porosity was calculated according to Eq. 1. Once the sample was dried at 105°C, water was added inside the test device to record added water weight until saturation. Three samples were examined to extract the average value.

$$n = \frac{V_{H_2O}}{V_{sample}} = \frac{w_{H_2O}/\rho_{H_2O}}{A*L} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where:

A: vessel area (cm²)

L: vessel length (cm)

w_{H_2O} : water weight for saturation of the sample (g)

ρ_{H_2O} : water density at 20°C (= 0.998 g/cm³)

Hydraulic conductivity calculation (k)

The hydraulic conductivity was calculated with the variable head method according to Darcy's law. A known volume of water (10 L) was instantly added to the column and the height of the water column above the material was recorded versus time. Hydraulic conductivity was calculated every 1cm drop between the initial 20 cm and last 5 cm, according to Eq. 2 (the bottom 5 cm were not recorded to avoid possible disturbance). Therefore, for each trial k was calculated as an average of 15 values.

$$k = \frac{L}{t_i - t_0} * \ln \left(\frac{h_0}{h_i} \right) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where:

L: filter media height (40 cm)

h_0, h_i : initial (20 cm), instant water height above the filter (cm)

t_0, t_i : start time (=0 s), time from measurement start for h_i recording (s)

This test was repeated until the pore volume factor (PVF) was equal to 20, as a material is considered to be saturated when PV gets replaced 20 times with new water (Wanigarathna et al., 2013).

Treatment start-up

Plants were not used in this experiment to avoid the long-term effect of the roots' development and test only the materials' contribution to the treatment. Start-up was performed with UASB effluent and the applied organic loading rate (OLR) was $5.5 \pm 0.8 \text{ gCOD m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, solids loading rate (SLR) was $2.8 \pm 0.5 \text{ gTSS m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and nitrogen loading rate (NLR) was $1.1 \pm 0.2 \text{ gNH}_4\text{-N m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. Feeding was intermittent respecting a hydraulic load of the unsaturated beds of 2 cm per flush.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Filling material properties

Biochar had similar granulometry with sand (control material) besides the very fine fragment ($<0.3 \text{ mm}$), which was crucial for the hydraulic behaviour, but was present at an accepted range ($\leq 10\%$). Both sand and biochar were quite uniform. Recycled glass was less uniform and very fines fragments were almost at the range of biochar (Figure 2). Regarding porosity, sand and glass had the same porosity explained by the similar origin of the two materials, while biochar had larger porosity. Gels' porosity was almost 1 since it was a water absorbent material, which could be expanded more than 100 times in volume terms (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Left: Granulometric curves for the test substrates. Right: Porosity of the test materials

Hydraulic performance

The hydraulic conductivity of the recycled glass was in the same order of magnitude with sand (0.16 and 0.22 cm/s, respectively), but its slower percolation was attributed to the presence of very fine fragments in a greater proportion than in sand. Biochar had the slowest percolation (0.04 cm/s), being almost 6 times slower than sand (Figure 3). The test repetition up to PVF 20 indicated that after only PVF 0-4 hydraulic conductivity was not stabilized for two out of the three materials, which was due to the presence of unsaturated zones inside the material and indicated the need for repetition. Due to the biochar slow percolation volume of added water among PVF 8 and PVF 20 no measurement was performed.

Figure 3. Hydraulic conductivity calculation up to PVF 20

Treatment performance

TSS and COD removal was high for all the tested materials except from gels' COD removal, which was due to the material's self-release of soluble COD. In the latter case, the large deviation of the results was due to the gradual decrease of this COD release, which is expected to further diminish (Figure 4). Ammonium removal was initially due to adsorption, while nitrification increased over time – except for biochar – as indicated by the large deviation of nitrate production (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Filling material's performance for TSS, COD, NH₄-N removal (average ± st.dev)

CONCLUSION

All the materials appeared to be suitable to use in unsaturated VSSF CWs applications based on their hydraulic performance and, according to the preliminary results of treatment performance, biofilm growth seemed possible to all materials.

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